

DESIGN OF EXPERIMENT: WOOD COMPOSITES BASED ON CROSSLINKED POLYPROPYLENE

A. Khongrit^{1,2*}, U. Meekum^{1,2}

¹ School of Polymer Engineering, Suranaree University of Technology,
Nakorn Ratchasima, Thailand

² Centre of Excellence for Petroleum, Petrochemicals, and Advanced Materials,
Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand

*holly2frozen@hotmail.com

Keywords: *Wood polypropylene composites, Crosslinked polypropylene, Design of experiment, sauna treatment*

1 General Introduction

Wood Plastic composites(WPCs) market is going strongly around the world. It is commonly used as substitute or alternate for the natural wood which is wildly prohibited or legally controlled by many countries. Most applications of WPCs are as structural and decorative materials such as outdoor deck, floors, windows and doors. The main ingredients of WPC consist of thermoplastic polymer matrix and natural fiber reinforcement. The most common matrices are PVC, PP and PE. The wood flour obtained from timber milling is commonly used. The characteristic of the product varied depend largely on type of matrix and reinforcement. However, the commercially available wood composite has some incompetency such as low mechanical properties compare to those hardwoods. Therefore, the improvements of the long term properties have been explored by many researchers and engineers. The main techniques used for diversifying of WPCs include grafting, cross linking and blending of the matrix and reinforced with other high performance filler(s)[1, 5, 6]. Silane grafting and water crosslinking of polyolefin have received much attention in industrial applications and fundamental research, because of its provide the obvious advantages, such as easy to process, low capital investment, and favorable properties in the processed materials[4]. Silane group is grafted onto the polymer chain by, firstly, addition of peroxide to initiate free radicals that can induce the grafting of a silane group onto the polymer backbone. The resultant silane grafted polymer matrices is then hydrolyzed and condense to create –Si–O–Si– bonds between the chains. The bonds between wood and

plastic have been suggested to comprise a mix of silane bridges and hydrogen bond[3]. This network results in the outstanding performance properties. In this studied, WPC based on crosslinked polypropylene and wood flour reinforcement was performed. As the crosslink structure of polymer chain enhances the properties of material such as higher in resistance to heat and outdoor degradation. Accordingly, it will give rise to superior in dimensional stability and durability. The statistical approach by mean of design of experimental(DOE) on the given constituent parameters that effect to the properties of WPC will be the prime interests.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Commercial grade isotactic polypropylene homopolymer(PP700J) for injection molding application(MFI = 12g/10min @230/2.16) supplied from SCG Chemical Co., Ltd. was used as the composite matrix. Vinyltrimethoxysilane(VTMS), Silquest A 171, as crosslinker or coupling agent was purchased from Optimal Tech Co., Ltd. General commercial grade Dicumyl peroxide(DCP) was employed as free radical initiator. Talc(JetFine 3CA) manufactured by Luzenac with the particle size of 1.1 µm was added as filler. Wood flour from timber mill was ground by hammer mill machine into fine powder with particle size, by mean of sieve size, less than 1 mm. Mixture of powders, Irganox 1076 and Irgafos 168, at weight ratio of 1:1 were used as thermal/processing stabilizer and available from Ciba specialty chemicals Co., Ltd.

2.2 Design of experiment

The 2^k factorial design of experiment was elected to optimal and quantify the amount of the composite constituents. Three parameters($k=3$) were silane(A), wood flour(B) and talc(C) contents. Each parameter was divided into two levels; high(+) and low(-), respectively. Also, in each level, it was sub-divided into two levels as shown in Table 1. For example, silane content at 3 and 5 phr were assigned as low level, vice versa 8 and 10 phr were assigned as high level, respectively. According to the factorial design, eight runs of WPC formula having the batch size corresponded to 300 g of PP were constructed as shown in Table 2. The statistical analyses were performed by using commercial computer software, Design Expert™.

2.3 WPC sample preparation

The reduced size wood flour was dried in hot oven at 105°C for at least 12 hr to eliminate the trace moisture. Wood flour, pre-weigh VTMS and process stabilizer powder was then vigorously mixed by high speed mixer for 5 minutes and stored overnight. PP pellet and solid DCP in tight seal container was warmed at approx. 50°C for a few minutes allowing the peroxide to be melted and then, rigorously pre-mixed. DCP was utterly coated onto polymer pellet. Talc and the silane treated wood flour were added and well incorporated with the pellet. The dry blend ingredient was kept in the oven 80°C before melt mixing. By using single screw feeder, the dried ingredient was then constantly fed into closely intermeshing co-rotation twin screw extruder (Brabender™) with screw diameter of 25 mm. and L/D of 20 The temperature profiles on the extruder for melt mixing from feed to die zones were 180, 185, 185, 190 and 190°C, respectively. The extrudate strand was air cooled and granulated in pellet using machine crusher. The test specimens were prepared by injection molding machine(Tederic TRX60c) with the barrel temperature of 190°C for all 4 zones. The wood polypropylene composites specimens were divided into 2 categories of samples. One was allowed to anneal at room temperature for at least a day and they are called *original sample*. The rest was incubated in the oven saturated with water vapor at 105°C, sauna oven, for 12 hours. The sauna incubation was employed to accelerate the

silane/water crosslink reaction. The sample obtained by this process was assigned as *sauna cured* or *cured WPC*.

Parameters	High level(+1)		Low level(-1)	
(A)Silane(phr)	10	8	5	3
(B)Wood Flour (phr)	45	35	25	15
(C)Talc (phr)	40	30	20	10

Table 1. The parameters and levels of the DOE.

Test No.	Silane(A) (phr)	Wood(B) (phr)	Talc(C) (phr)	DCP (phr)
1	3(-1)	25(-1)	20(-1)	0.3
2	5(-1)	15(-1)	40(+1)	0.3
3	3(-1)	45(+1)	10(-1)	0.3
4	5(-1)	35(+1)	30(+1)	0.3
5	8(+1)	15(-1)	10(-1)	0.3
6	10(+1)	25(-1)	40(+1)	0.3
7	8(+1)	35(+1)	20(-1)	0.3
8	10(+1)	45(+1)	30(+1)	0.3

Table 2. The factorial DOE matrix for crosslinked PP WPC.

2.4 Properties measurement and testing

Melt flow index at 170/2.16 of wood composite was determined according to ASTM D1238. Flexural properties of the wood composites was obtained according to ASTM D790 using the Instron universal testing machine(UTM, model 5565). Notched and unnotched Izod impact strength of the composite sample was tested in accordance with ASTM D256. Both flexural and impact properties were conducted at room temperature. The ASTM D648 testing with the standard load of 0.455 MPa(66 psi) and heating rate of $2\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ was followed to measure the heat deflection temperature(HDT) of the sample. These engineered properties obtained from both original and cured samples were employed as the respond analysis in DOE. Morphology of the impact fractured surface was examined by scanning electron microscope(SEM). The samples were ionized coating with gold before investigation.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 DOE Analysis

Notched and unnotched impacts, flexural strength and modulus, HDT and MFI results obtained from the standard tests are summarized in Table 3(a) and 3(b), respectively. The test values generally show that the sauna cured has superior effect on the measured properties as they are increased after the incubation process. Using the Design Expert®, statistical analysis of the responds data are performed. For the flexural strength, the plot of normal probability against the standardized effects and also the ANOVA summary is shown in Fig. 1(a) and 1(b), for original and sauna cured of WPC samples, respectively. The figures show that silane content(A) and interaction between silane and talc content(AC) are the greatest effect on flexural strength of WPC. They are positive(+) and negative(-) effects, respectively, for both original and cured. Applying the ANOVA testing at 95% of confidential, the test result confirms that those two effects are significant effects on the flexural of WPC. Taking only flexural strength of WPC, the DOE outcome suggests that adding silane at high concentration would increase the chain network bridge between matrix and fiber, and hence increasing in flexural strength. Again, by applying the flexural modulus as the design respond, the probability plot are shown in Fig. 2(a) and 2(b) for the original and cured samples. The graphs demonstrate that +C have the greatest effect to the modulus of original and cured WPC. The ANOVA testing result also concludes that this parameter is significantly and positively effect, as *p*-value below 0.05, on the modulus. It means that incorporating talc at high content would give rise to higher in the flexural modulus, more stiff material, of the WPC. By analysis of notched Izod impact strength of both conditioned samples that are given in Fig. 3(a) and 3(b). It is indicated that there is no significant effect from the given parameter on the impact properties for both original and cured samples. Similarly for the unnotched test results for the original sample as show in figure 4(a), it is found that there is no significantly affect on the respond. On the other hand for the values obtained from cured WPC as seen in Fig. 4(b), the variable A+, B- and C- have tendency to be significant parameters for this respond. As expect, the ANOVA results confirm that they are the significant ones which are similar to those flexure strength. It is strengthen that higher in silane and lower in talc contents will produce WPC with high

fracture toughness after sauna cured process. By analyzing the rest of the respond with identical manner together with the ANOVA conclusion, the regression model for prediction the properties WPC based on crosslinked PP prepared from wood flour, talc and silane can be constructed and summarized in Table 4. It is manifested that the wood flour(B+) and talc(C+) at high level obviously increased HDT of the uncured WPC but shows no significant effect for the sauna cured. Finally for the melt flow index, it is increased by decreasing the flour content(B-). According to the regression model presented in Table 4, the parameters seen in the equations are the significant parameter by mean of ANOVA analysis and it can be used to predict the properties figure of the WPC. For example, the equation for heat deflection temperature of the original is $138.52+2.81(B)+1.81(C)$. It is implied that maximize HDT of WPC can be achieved if it is compounded in twin screw mixing and injected at 190°C by using wood flour(B+) and tacl(+C) at high levels(= +1). The rest can be estimated as the same approach.

Run	MFI (g/10min)	Flexural strength(MPa)		Flexural modulus(GPa)	
		original	cured	original	cured
1	12.27	53.6	53.6	1.84	1.96
2	11.63	55.6	54.2	2.34	2.41
3	8.61	53.8	53.6	2.16	2.18
4	9.02	54.7	55.7	2.34	2.35
5	20.40	55.9	57.7	1.84	1.89
6	12.54	54.7	54.1	2.43	2.58
7	9.95	56.1	57.4	2.29	2.23
8	7.24	55.8	56.0	2.47	2.57

(a)

Run	Notched impact(kJ/m ²)		Unnotched impact(kJ/m ²)		HDT(°C)	
	original	cured	original	cured	original	cured
1	1.09	1.34	8.75	9.66	131	136
2	0.91	1.27	9.18	7.70	138	138
3	1.11	1.32	7.56	8.69	141	141
4	0.99	1.35	7.33	6.28	141	143
5	0.96	1.35	8.92	11.48	134	140
6	1.06	1.41	8.02	8.54	139	142
7	1.11	1.43	9.49	8.96	140	139
8	1.31	1.12	9.11	8.50	142	142

(b)

Table 3 (a) MFI and flexural properties and (b) impact strengths and HDT of the original and sauna cured WPCs, respectively.

Fig 1. Normal probability plots of Flexural strength (a) original and (b) cured.

Fig 2. Normal probability plots of Flexural modulus (a) original and (b) cured.

Fig 3. Normal probability plots of notched impact strength (a) original and (b) cured.

Fig 4. Normal probability plots of unnotched impact strength (a) original and (b) cured.

Test	Regressed models
Original:	
MFI	11.46-2.75(B)
Flexural strength	55.01+0.61(A)-0.55(AC)
Flexural modulus	2.21+0.11(B) +0.19(C)-0.098(BC)
Notched impact	No significant
Unnotched impact	No significant
HDT	138.52+2.81(B)+1.81(C)
Sauna Cured:	
Flexural strength	55.20+1.12(A)-0.41(C)-0.83 (AC)
Flexural modulus	2.27+0.20(C)
Notched impact	No significant
Unnotched impact	8.64+0.73(A)-0.53(B)-0.88(C)+0.46(ABC)
HDT	No significant

Table 4. The predicted regression model for the properties of WPCs derived from ANOVA testing.

3.2 Scanning electron microscopy(SEM)

SEM photographs of the fractured surface of crosslinked polypropylene wood composites are shown in Fig. 5(a) to 5(f). Fig. 5(a) and 5(b) illustrates the surface of WPC using lowest silane content(Test#1) before and after sauna cured, respectively. There is an indication of poor adhesion between wood and matrix as evidence by gap between wood and PP phase. Vice versa, the interfacial adhesion between these two phases is improved after the curing. By increasing the silane content to high level, 8 phr, as from the Test#7 and shown the highest impact strength, the electron photographs of the surface are given in Fig. 5(c), 5(d), for original and cured WPC, respectively. It is obviously seen that the interfacial bonding between matrix and fiber is improved. Especially, when it was undergone sauna incubation. Further increasing silane, wood and talc contents as for Test#8, the interfacial bonding of the composite is retained as evidenced in Fig.5(e) and 5(f). The SEM photographs suggest that the interfacial bonding of WPC specimen is achieved through silane/water the crosslink reaction. Hence, the crosslink bridge between polymer matrix and wood fiber could play the important role for enhance the surface interaction and bonding strength between matrix and reinforcement. Accordingly, within the upper/lower limits of this research, adding the silane content at high levels would increase the mechanical properties, especially fracture toughness, of the WPC. However, further increase the fiber content beyond the upper limit, the particle become too dense in the matrix. Therefore, stress transfer from matrix to filler and

flexibility of chain is inferior. As the result, the impact toughness would be decreased [2].

Fig 5. SEM micrograph of (a) Test#1(original), (b)Test#1(cured), (c) Test#7(original), (d) Test#7 (cured) (e) Test#8(original) and (f) Test#8 (cured) at magnitude of X500.

4 Conclusions

From the design of experiment approach to validate the optimal contents of WPC constituents based on crosslinked PP as the matrix, it was found that compounding of WPC at high level(+) of silane, wood flour and talc content produced the composite with generally good mechanical and thermal properties. Sauna cured via silane/water macro crosslinked reaction facilitated the interfacial adhesion between fibre and matrix and hence enhanced the mechanical properties. Further increased in the constituent portion would diminish the toughness of the sample as fibre/filler become

aggregate into large particle and too dense. Moreover, incorporating the wood fibre/filler at high load gives rise to the lower in melt index that make the WPC difficult to flow during processing.

References

- [1] C. Clemons. "Elastomer modified polypropylene-polyethylene blends as matrices for wood flour-plastic composites". *Composites: part A*, Vol. 41, pp 1559-1569, 2010.
- [2] G.B. Hattotuwa., H. I. Premalal. and A. Baharin. "Comparison of the mechanical properties of rice husk powder filled polypropylene composites with talc filled polypropylene composites". *Polymer Testing*, Vol. 21, pp 833–839, 2002.
- [3] G. Grubbstrom. and, K. Oksman. "Influence of wood flour moisture content on the degree of silane-crosslinking and its relationship to structure–property relations of wood thermo-plastic composites". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol.69, pp 1045–1050, 2009.
- [4] K. Sirisinha. and K. Kawko. "Properties and characterization of filled poly(Propylene) composites crosslinked through siloxane linkage" *Macromolecular Materials and Engineering*, Vol. 290, pp 128-135, 2005.
- [5] M. Bengtsson. and K. Oksman. "Silane crosslink wood plastic composite: processing and properties". *Composites science and technology*, Vol. 66, pp 2177-2186, 2006.
- [6] Y. Lei, Q. Wu, C. M. Clemons, F. Yoa, and Y. Xu. "Influence of Nanoclay on Properties of HDPE/ Wood Composites". *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol. 106, pp 3958 – 3966, 2007.